

Boosting European Citizens' Knowledge and Awareness
of Bio-Economy Research and Innovation

D 5.3

Validated monitoring results

Report

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1. Executive summary

This deliverable reports on all evaluation and monitoring activities in BLOOM. The validated evaluation and monitoring results are based on the evaluation criteria developed in D5.1 and D5.2. Deliverable 5.1 provides the evaluation strategy of the project BLOOM. All qualitative and quantitative instruments applied in the BLOOM project are provided in D5.2.

The evaluation pursued two distinctive approaches, the formative and the summative evaluation. The formative evaluation aimed at accompanying the BLOOM project and allowed a continuous evaluation of how and if the objectives of the project BLOOM were met in order to set specific measures or adaptations during the project to improve the outcome of the project and with that supporting a reflective process.

The summative part of the BLOOM evaluation focuses on the impact of the interventions on the target groups reached and therefore focuses on the objectives and output of the project.¹ Summative evaluation is outcome focused rather than process focussed. Thus, the summative evaluation is more anchored in quantitative methods of data collection. It is applied during the implementation of the project and at the end of it. This approach helps the project to measure if it has met its goals, if there were any unintended consequences, which learnings happened and how to improve. Methods used in this regard are questionnaires, feedback polls etc. This approach was particularly important for the outreach activities and materials developed in BLOOM.

This report follows the structure of the different project activities and shows how evaluation was applied and with which results. Section 2.1 compiles evaluation activities applied within the consortium. It describes how feedback was gathered during consortium meetings, how processes were monitored in regular online surveys for WP leaders, and how oral feedback was given during the monthly calls of the consortium.

Section 2.2 encompasses all tasks carried out in order to feedback results to the hub leaders and support improving. It shows regular feedback loops as applied in the monthly calls, tells about cross fertilisation meetings of hub leaders, and so called “hub alignment calls” which were carried out between individual hub leaders, the hub coordinator (WP 3 leader), the project coordinator and the WP 1 leaders for quality assurance of communicated content.

The entire section 3 describes the evaluation of the school network activities (as outlined in WP 4). It provides results of the various evaluation instruments used for the different school network activities.

Section 4 is dedicated to the evaluation results of the hub activities. It contains the analyses of all hub activities from co-creation processes to outreach activities and is mainly based on the reporting templates filled out by the hub leaders.

Section 5 collects some reflections, including adaptations according to the growing COVID Pandemic.

Section 6 gives an overview on the web statistics for the BLOOM website.

Finally, section 7 provides a summary of results achieved, contrasting the objectives formulated in D5.1 within the evaluation strategy of BLOOM.

¹ See also:

http://evaluationtoolbox.net.au/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=40&Itemid=126 [2018-09-10]

2. Internal communication and procedural improvement

2.1 BLOOM consortium: internal communication and procedural improvement

The formative evaluation in BLOOM focused on two main categories namely the “interactive category” and the “monitoring category”. Both categories were part of the project implementation and helped to improve the design and communication of the project BLOOM continuously. For that interviews, focus groups, questionnaires, online surveys, involvement and recommendations of an advisory board etc. were applied. The monitoring also helped to ensure that the project activities were being delivered efficiently and effectively. Budget tracking, time tracking, questionnaires, and regular internal online surveys supported this approach. The formative evaluation fostered an exploration of the project process from various viewpoints (participants, project staff and other stakeholders).²

Feedback questionnaires at consortium meetings

The target group of these questionnaires was the BLOOM consortium. After each meeting questionnaires are collected to improve all BLOOM meetings. ZSI provided all partners with feedback questionnaires after the project consortium meetings. These questionnaires are evaluated by ZSI. This means ZSI collected the data, analysed them and shared the results within the consortium. The consortium meetings aimed at enabling constructive exchange between all partners. The answers supported the team to identify specific needs and communication deficits. Results fed into the organisation of the next upcoming consortium meetings and also helped local meeting hosts to adopt accordingly. The questionnaire was slightly adopted from meeting to meeting.

The consortium meetings questionnaires should collect feedback from the consortium partners on structure, length and organisation of the meeting in order to improve the settings if needed. But mainly, the feedback was meant to steer the further project process. Questions were directed towards certain content that was discussed in the meeting and asked whether this content had been adequately discussed. Questions like or “I have gained a common understanding of bioeconomy” “the dissemination strategy is clear to me” should give feedback if consortium members could clearly understand this content. It also addressed next steps in the project to make sure if partners understood well their upcoming tasks, like “The next steps in the project are clear to me”. Questions like: “I feel confident in making my own mobile videos” or “I feel confident with preparing and facilitating my co-creation workshops” should tell if partners were clear about specific tasks. Mostly, questions like these were answered rather positively by the participants. Also, the general question which was frequently asked in all questionnaires “overall, the meeting was useful for me” was answered positively throughout the surveys. Open questions asked for recommen-

² See also:

http://evaluationtoolbox.net.au/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=24&Itemid=125 [2020-04-24]

dations for future meetings. Here, often the request for “more time” was brought up, not only “for discussions”, “questions and answers” and “informing”, also time outside the agenda, for “bilateral meetings” and “informal encounter” was requested. These suggestions were taken up by the management and hosting teams.

Regular online surveys for WP leaders

Online surveys for WP leaders should help to enable a smooth project process and therefore aimed at monitoring the progress of each work package according to the relevance of activities, the efficiency, the effectiveness, and the impact orientation of the activities implemented. Thus, additionally to virtual meetings all WP leaders were encouraged to fill in this questionnaire, to summarize the specific process within their WP, identify possible problems and share success stories. The results of these regular surveys were shared among the whole consortium and helped the team to always stay tuned. Thus, upcoming difficulties could be identified and addressed timely.

The polls with the questionnaire were conducted three times throughout the project duration and contained quantitative and qualitative questions. This allowed us to grasp detailed explanations of the quantitative answers and gave room for specific suggestions for improvement. The technology used was Lime-survey. The answers were analysed using descriptive analysis.

Oral feedback in the monthly calls

The BLOOM consortium can be regarded as a learning community. While implementing the project activities, constant exchange and reflection gained new insights that were shared among the partners and were applied in upcoming activities. As WP 5 leaders the ZSI team therefore gathered lessons learnt and gave oral feedback in monthly calls of the consortium and the team members also took part in regular hub exchange meetings (conducted by WP 3).

The feedback and inputs were given based on to the data, which were gathered via various channels, such as reporting templates (see section 4), deliverables written by partners, work package online surveys, results of evaluation questionnaires after consortium meetings, online questionnaires filled in by outreach participants, alignment calls with WP leaders, inputs collected from the PO and our AB members, and last but not least recommendations given from the virtual EC project review.

The topics discussed were manifold and addressed all work packages. With WP 1 a constant development of quality assurance could be established, providing the partners materials for their outreach work (such as key messages) as well as checks of their materials. In WP 2 mainly inputs could be given according to the interactive parts of the BLOOM website and the social media streams. WP 3 topics not only addressed aspects concerning the individual hubs, such as outreach formats, target groups, materials used etc, but also collaborations and activities across hubs and interlinkages to other WPs, mainly with WP 1 and 6. For WP 4 results of online questionnaires could be fed back to the EUN team. Amongst others, another topic of WP 6 was how to increase the BLOOM presence, especially in the scientific community, in which finally all WPs could contribute.

2.2 Hub coordination

Feedback loops

Monthly online meetings served for an internal exchange among all consortium members and gave insight on the work carried out by each work package. Not only the “outreach” work package leaders reported (WP 2, 3, 4), but partners asked in particular for feedback from WP 5, mainly on the reporting they had provided on their activities and the feedback participants of these activities had given. The WP 5 team reported on current results and put them up for discussion during these meetings to ask questions, to clarify details and to ensure that everything is filled out correctly and understandably. Furthermore, the WP 5 team gave direct feedback to the hub leaders on their reports to ask questions to clarify details and to ensure that everything is filled out correctly and understandably in the templates (see section 4). Revised reports were uploaded to the shared Moodle platform and thus open accessible for all project partners.

Two cross-fertilization meetings

Besides the online exchange and regular consortium meetings, hub partners had two further opportunities for exchange and learning from each other. The first one was held in 2018 at the university in Wageningen and was a co-creation training, provided by the ZSI team. This two-days training was an introduction to the topic of co-creation and also offered the opportunity to try out some of the presented methods. With the help of design thinking techniques, partners were able to develop creative ideas for their outreach formats and also get feedback on them. What hub leaders learned should help them to carry out co-creation processes in the hubs themselves.

The second one was an outreach-coordination meeting, which was held in December 2019 in Bonn right in the middle of the outreach phase and offered another opportunity for exchange on outreach activities and how to overcome some challenges which have occurred along the way. In working groups the hubs collaborated on common problem solving and in addition, they developed cross-hub activities for the following months.

Hub alignment calls

The hub alignment calls were part of the formative evaluation reacting to a need identified by WP5, WP1 and WP3. The alignment calls took place between December 2019 and July 2020; with the leaders from WP5, WP1, WP3 and one hub or co-hub. The alignment calls were an important activity for the BLOOM hubs; they allowed reflection, and in some cases the activities were significantly changed and adapted after the discussion, in one case the repetition of specific outreach activities was agreed on. In some cases all activities were successfully completed and the call was more important for WP3 and WP5 to get a complete picture and overview of the achievements. Even in those hubs during the discussion more activities came up that were not reported yet – but were important for BLOOM.

The alignment calls’ topics were first to get an overview of activities, the reporting of the activities, the cooperation between hubs and co-hubs which was not always smooth; but there were clear efforts to make the collaboration better. Difficulties involved personnel changes leading to difficulties in communication, language barriers and different focus or

development of bioeconomy strategies between countries. Further the alignment calls discussed the co-creation in the hubs. The discussion showed that co-creation was an ongoing process throughout the project and will in some cases even go on after BLOOM is completed. Some of the outcomes of the co-creation workshops were not feasible within the project duration and specifications; therefore, only feasible results were implemented. Target groups and how to approach them were discussed, as well as the use of BLOOM materials especially from WP1 in the outreach activities. The last topic of the alignment call was the network extension in the region. The discussions showed a mixed scenarios depending strongly on the context of the respective regions.

- DE: Network extension is difficult in Nordrhein-Westfalen.
 - On one hand, the networks are already formed between industry, policy makers and research and are not open to civil society.
 - On the other hand, bioeconomy in this region compared to other regions is rather developed and there are many actors working in communication of bioeconomy, therefore it proves to be a competitive field. Not easy to overcome for WILAB but they were persistent.
- AT:
 - With government: Unsure due to new government. The topic of bioeconomy now falls under two ministries. EFE is making efforts to build strong relationships with representatives from both ministries
 - Flourishing with companies
- FI: BLOOM has not had much effect with regards to JAMK collaborating with local and regional relevant organisations as this was already quite strong prior to BLOOM. However, through the BLOOM activities they can say that they have come closer to high schools.
- SE: VA has gained more connections and interactions at regional and national level esp. with industry. VA already gained reputation as a connector in this field. VA was asked to be part of initiatives, projects, invited to present, are possible partners for future projects, or they could supply information on BE.
- ES: BLOOM and especially its involvement in the bioeconomy cluster and strategy in the Andalusia region has strengthened the relationship with bioeconomy in the region. It has created an informal space to discuss and create activities in the topic of bioeconomy. Furthermore, BLOOM's engagement has also led to other collaborations e.g. the region and consumer/producer organisations. BLOOM's activities have also had an impact on researchers in that now they identify that they were actually working on bioeconomy all along.
- PL (UAK): Network building has been both negative and positive. At the beginning, building of the network was very difficult. However, with time people became more interested as they realised that bioeconomy and circular economy were important topics for the EU; and as a result, there was funding available. Generally, for the network building, UAK feels that the institutions are less important. It makes more sense to concentrate on some individual people who are engaged in this topic e.g. they have good collaborations with individual people involved in bioplastics, bio-

gas, H2o2o Polish bioeconomy project, professors from the university. People who are engaged want to engage: “cooperation of the willing”

- NL: The Emmen region was open to the involvement of BLOOM. BLOOM has created some dynamics in the region that were not there before. Cooperation in the region could be stronger especially with regards to connection to triple helix partners. This would ensure stronger sustainability for BLOOM activities. Not sure if the momentum BLOOM brought, will still there when the project ends, we could work on better organising the network, see that they have a regular meeting, to keep it going.

3. Evaluation of BLOOM Schoolnetwork activities

The following activities took place in the BLOOM school network /WP4 aiming at raising awareness and knowledge on bioeconomy and innovation for young citizens:

Co-creating BLOOM Learning Scenarios with BLOOM teachers: 20 teachers from 10 different countries co-created bioeconomy teaching resources for STEM classes for primary and secondary education. For that the teachers had several numerous online meetings and two workshops face to face in Brussels, their activities included also testing and improving the materials created. Each workshop and meeting was evaluated. The activities led to five learning scenarios for STEM classes for different school levels – which became the BLOOM school box. The testing was done not only by the own authors but also by the other pilot teachers to ensure they could really be used by less experienced teachers and in many different contexts (subjects, curricula, countries, cultures). For testing and implementing, the BLOOM school box all teachers filled in the provided reporting template after testing. The results were collected by EUN. The reporting can be read in D4.1 – BLOOM school box.

Teacher trainings represented an important and strategic component for the dissemination and uptake of innovative STEM practices, and for the BLOOM project in particular, the uptake of bioeconomy by young citizens. One of the core ideas behind the teacher trainings was that it helped introducing the concept of bioeconomy in even more classrooms. Exact number of trainings and results from the internal reporting of the teachers can be seen in D4.3 – Report on international and national teacher trainings.

The BLOOM **MOOC** represented a further important step in raising awareness of bioeconomy among educators and in scaling up the use of the pedagogical resources on bioeconomy including the BLOOM School Box. More than 800 teachers followed the course, and more than 250 successfully completed the course and received a certification. For the BLOOM MOOC the participants filled in a pre- and a post- questionnaire. For evaluation of the registration and the course including results of the Pre- and Post-MOOC questionnaires please see D4.5 – MOOC development and outreach report.

Two competitions were organised, one in 2019 and one in 2020. The first competition under the title BLOOM “Teach bioeconomy!” competition was restricted to MOOC participants. As a result six additional bioeconomy teaching learning scenarios were made available in the BLOOM School Box. The topics included Bioeconomy awareness; biotechnology techniques; bioenergy and our lives; the benefits of composting; and biofuel production from fruit waste.

The second competition was an extra activity of EUN and not required in the DoA. It was organised as part of the STEM Discovery Campaign 2020 and supported by Scientix and aimed at further raising awareness of bioeconomy among the wider public which once again inspired teachers to use the bioeconomy teaching resources included in the BLOOM School Box.

The report on the first competition can be found in D4.4 – School competition framework. A report on the second competition is included in D4.3 – Report on national and international teacher trainings.

Results of teacher training questionnaire

In the following we include the evaluation of the teacher training questionnaires. All other activities were thoroughly evaluated in the respective deliverables of WP4 as indicated above.

The involved teachers in developing and co-creating the BLOOM school materials (10 coordination teachers plus 10 support teachers) were committed to hold 1-2 teacher trainings in their schools in order to disseminate the content and use of the school materials in BLOOM. Some of these trainings were held in an international context (at a conference, etc.) reaching also teachers from other countries (see D4.3). The participants were teachers and were after the training supposed to apply the material in their classes with their students. After the training, organised and held by the 20 involved BLOOM teachers, the participants received a questionnaire indicating how they experienced the training and the content of the training in local languages. The trainers provided answers in an online tool. Through that ZSI collected the anonymised data.

The following table shows the absolute number of trainings and participants in the respective countries of the BLOOM teachers.

Table 1: Number of the teacher trainings, participants and teachers who implemented BLOOM School (Source: D4.3)

No of:	Austria	Belgium	Spain	Greece	Croatia	Israel	Italy	Poland	Portugal	Sweden	Total
Trainings	1	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	16
Participants	24	10	31	29	10	14	36	11	14	23	202
Trained teachers	5	5	5	5	10	5	5	5	-	4	49

From 202 participants 137 filled out the questionnaire. Respondents indicated to teach the following subjects, multiple answers were possible.

Figure 1: Subjects participants teach

Most of the teachers that participated taught in secondary school level (54%), 37% in primary school level. Some participants worked with adults, but there were also a couple of pre-service teachers and researchers talking part in the training.

The age of the students in the graphic below shows that the highest involvement occurred in the age of 14-18. This correlates with the fact that teachers of this level were most strongly represented in the trainings and also that there were more education resources co-created for this age group. The topic of bioeconomy is highly complex, however teachers involved in the process wished for more time and resources in order to be able to co-create more teaching resources for younger students as well.

Figure 2: Age of pupils

In the questionnaire the five BLOOM school box curricula were evaluated by the participants:

- **Bloom your school with your biofuel and soap lab** (Authors: Teachers from Sweden & Greece; Subjects covered: Science, Biology, Chemistry, Physics, Technology and Arts; Age of students: 13 - 16 years old).
- **Examining the thermal properties of bio-based building materials** (Authors: Teachers from Poland & Austria; Subjects covered: Physics (standard and higher level), Mathematics, Chemistry, Biology; Age of students: 16 – 19 years old).
- **Building a new environmental Future** (Authors: Teachers from Portugal & Israel; Subjects covered: Biology, Chemistry, Biochemistry, Geology, Natural Science; Age of students: Adaptable for different levels and ages, primary and secondary. For younger students 13 -15 years old and for older students 15 -17 years old).
- **How poop will change the world** (Authors: Teachers from Croatia & Spain; Subjects covered: Physics, Chemistry and Biology; Age of students: 13-15 years old or 10-12 years old.)
- **Growing plastic and new life for plastic** (Authors: Teachers from Belgium & Italy; Subjects covered: Biology, Technology, Engineering, Environmental Education, Chemistry, Statistics; Age of students: 11-18 years old)

Figure 3: Rating of school box curricula

The graphic above shows that the five BLOOM school box curricula were evaluated differently. Altogether, 70% of participants indicated that the BLOOM teaching resources are useful for their classes. 20% indicated that they might not or hardly be useful. 10 % did not rate the respective material. The best evaluation received curricula number 5 on growing plastic. 90% of the teachers indicated that the teaching materials were very useful for their teaching. 53% perceived the soap lab as very useful or useful while 29% perceived it as not or hardly useful.

Figure 4: Rating of school box curricula

The trainings received very positive feedback, 90% of the participants indicated that the event fully achieved its expecting learning outcomes and that they enjoyed the event. 90% stated that they learnt at the event how to link STEM with bioeconomy and on how to teach bioeconomy on the context of real life. 47% of the participants indicated it very likely and 38% as likely that the event would improve their teaching at school. 87% thought about sharing the content in school and that the teaching material was going to help pupils' learning in STEM subjects. Participants also assumed to 90% that taking up the BLOOM school box would improve pupils' knowledge and interest in STEM and other careers. And 88% would recommend the training to colleagues.

4. Evaluation of Hub activities

After the co-creation and outreach activities all hub partners filled in a reporting template which helped them to document their experiences and results. The template supported the hub teams reflecting about the process and also gave insights into what worked well and what did not work. Content but also design and organisation were qualitatively evaluated with the help of these templates. All templates have been qualitatively analysed and coded with the MAXQDA software, structure and categorised. Each of these sub topics are narratively in the following sections. A list of all co-creation and outreach activities can be found in D3,5 annex.

4.1. Co-creation activities

The co-creation workshops were one of the key parts in the BLOOM project. After being trained and being provided ideas for methodologies and a suggestion for such a workshop process, all hub teams involved a diverse group of stakeholders to co-create innovative and successful outreach activities and/or materials. Each hub adapted methodologies and processes to their specific needs. Some split the process in several steps, starting with identifying target groups and co-designing personas for identifying their target groups accordingly and later collecting and co-designing outreach ideas tailored to these target groups. In some cases a last step aimed at fine tuning the outreach activity to enable the implementation. In total the BLOOM hubs implemented 30 co-creation activities and engaged a total of 163 participants in these processes.

Most co-creation workshops took place face to face. However, the BLOOM team had to react on the corona pandemic and additionally used a format they called “co-creation webinar” for the last step in their co-creation process, which was fine-tuning an outreach idea. In the reporting and reflection sections these two co-creation webinars are also included.

4.1.1 Interim Evaluation

The WP 5 team reported on interim evaluation results (for the consortium meeting in June 2019 in Arterra) to give hub leaders first feedback on activities carried out and to improve further co-creation processes accordingly. This interim report showed statistics on the activities undertaken up to that point in time, and audiences and stakeholder groups reached. It became clear that no precise numbers of reached audiences could have been stated as there different categories and names have been used. Therefore, the reporting template had to be adapted by the WP 5 team, clear categories of target groups were pre-defined and hub leaders had to indicate precise numbers. The reports also provided information about the setting and location of the first co-creation workshops. Fortunately, it was easily recognizable that hub leaders could have make good use of the co-creation training held in Wageningen as they had been looking for nice and sometimes rather unusual locations for their workshops and emphasised important aspects such as “nice atmosphere, bright light, comfortable open space, cosy, full of plants ...etc” (PPT WP 5 CM Arterra). Hubs also reported on methods applied at their co-creation workshops. In this respect, too, they were able to draw on what they had learned from the co-creation training. Methods such as warm-up exercise in the beginning, brainstorming, roundtable discussion, the Avatar/Persona development, „speed boat method“, “ideation“, World café or future sentences have been applied. Hub leaders struggled with the reactions of their participants as they had to apply sometimes not too well known techniques “people were a bit reserved to participate in rather experimental methods to co-create content” (hub reporting) and had to get used to the methods by themselves as well: *“the participatory methodology is going itself the main barrier in order to get an effective dialogue and information from the hub’s members”* (hub reporting). Hub leaders reported on knowledge on bio economy of their workshop participants which was rather low and on their attitudes on it which was mainly rather positive. These first findings could be confirmed at later stages in the project as well. Hub leaders could gather the needs of their participants on how they could spark interest and learn more on bioeconomy. This comprised

aspects such as: “learning from others, considering new perspectives, understanding different applications for bioeconomy” and also being confronted with a “critical approach to the concept of bioeconomy”. Therefore, activities should “showcase different new applications and innovations”, “showing alternative material options”, but also “discussing necessary rules and norms to avoid undesired consequences”. Also transparency was an important issue: „they wanted more invisibility in the whole production chain so that it would be easier for the consumer to compare between a bio-based and a traditional product. These improvements would raise the interest of an ordinary consumer” (hub reporting). These and other mentioned needs were considered by later project activities.

4.1.2 Reporting and reflection

In this section the results of the reporting and reflection activity after the co-creation workshops is summarized. It gives an overview on setting, participants and which stakeholder group they belong to and which knowledge about bioeconomy they had, and what their attitude towards the topic was like, the outreach ideas they co-created, and which content, target groups, and formats these ideas include. At the end reflections and lessons learnt by the hubs are collected.

Recruitment and participants

The hubs gathered different experiences in their recruitment process. Most of them sent out email invitations and as next steps conducted phone calls. Combining these two steps was reported as a very successful recruitment process. However, this approach was not the only one. Invitation were of course shared on websites, social media and newsletter, but the most promising processes were different kinds of personal contacts. Having the chance to personally talk to potential future workshop participants promised to be a suitable approach. Hubs used personal contacts, contacts from events or contacts through representative organisations. Another option described in the reportings was the combination with already planned events such as conferences or seminars at university, in case the group there was complement with the aimed participant target group(s).

The BLOOM co-creation activities aimed at engaging **five stakeholder groups**: Science Education, Research, Business and Industry, Policy and Civil Society. The hubs managed to get representatives of these groups as participants in most of their activities. However, some hubs were struggling to find representatives from civil society and others struggled with representatives from business and industry.

Some co-creation activities actively aimed at finding participants from homogenous groups to meet their needs. Especially when it comes to engaging young people, this approach was chosen.

Most of the co-creation workshop groups had great diversity in age, pre-knowledge and gender, even though in total slightly more women than men participated in the activities.

Content of workshops and outreach formats

Before giving insights in the content of the co-creation workshops and most important of the latter outreach activities, it must be said that the hubs implemented their processes with more diverse groups, as the aforementioned. In most cases the groups started from very different pre-knowledge backgrounds on bioeconomy. It was of high importance for all groups to find a common understanding or at least a definition of the concept of bioeconomy to further be able to constructively work on outreach activities. Some hub leaders provided definitions from the national or regional bioeconomy strategy which they used as basis for their discussions; others implemented dedicated sessions to find a common understanding of the topic, which included interview sessions among participants, presentations of experts, or common picture methodologies. The hub experiences showed that a common understanding of the concept of bioeconomy is not necessarily interlinked with pre-knowledge about the topic. Even groups where all participants are directly involved with bioeconomy struggled to find this common understanding. In general all hubs reported that it was important to strive for a common understanding and define a common starting point to be able to have fruitful discussions.

Also attitudes towards the topic were very diverse among the co-creation participants. Probably depending on their background and experiences, some were more critical about the topic while others were fully optimistic about the potentials of bioeconomy.

In some workshops the teams mainly focussed on the potentials of the bioeconomy seeing its potential to promote more sustainable materials and tackle global problems such as waste. The teams working in the northern hub, for instance, were aware of the huge potential of wood-based products in the future markets. However, hub leaders emphasized that the group wanted a more transparent production chain that consumers could compare between bio-based and traditional products. Also other hub leaders talked about a rather positive attitude among their participants. They highlighted the fact that there are almost no boundaries, that there is the potential for enhancing business with sustainable solutions, or that they see bioeconomy as an area of development of professional life, sustainability and business. In general, the reporting let assume that positive attitudes overweighed among the participants and throughout the discussion, even though it was repeatedly mentioned, that it is important to include critical perspectives or establish certain ground rules addressing critical aspects such as linkages with living standards of consumers and the communication about reducing consumption, land requirements for a modified and expanded production of biological raw materials, greenwashing and so on.

As the hub leaders of the Austrian hubs has put it: *“When discussing the bioeconomy, several concerns and fears were mentioned such as the increasing financialization of nature, the substitution of disposable products with biobased disposables, heightened emissions through the possible reduction of carbon sinks (e.g. forests) and accelerated biodiversity loss. [...] it was suggested that there is a need to establish certain ground rules and incorporate norms to avoid undesired consequences.”* (Austrian hub).

Target groups and Needs

The workshop participants have defined different target groups they aimed at. The needs which could be identified vary from general needs regarding the bioeconomy to target group specific needs. For example, there is a general need for a common concept of bioeconomy or the need to show different new applications and innovations that bioeconomy has to offer. For instance, according to participants in the Spanish hub there is the need to configure bioeconomy as a multi-stakeholder environment where society, private, public and academic sectors are involved, and foster its potential for the job market. Additionally the teams emphasized the importance of raising awareness among different target groups they had identified but also the society as such. Connected to this aim is the challenge of communication of the topic. How can bioeconomy best be communicated with and to the public and how can their knowledge and interest be increased and critical thinking fostered. Creating school materials and exchange with environmental organisations or even movements were ideas in that regard. Other co-creation teams focused more on transparency and identified needs regarding production chains. Different information and content needs to be accessible and understandable for different target groups. People need to know about environmental impacts of products or materials and how recycling processes work. Thus, a platform gathering information from researchers and companies and providing space for information which is needed to make sustainable choices as a consumer was wished for.

If we go in more detail and have a look which needs the teams identified for the target groups, we see that these differ a bit from each other. Considering young people and the research community there is the need to make young people aware of new bio-based products and thus to generally engage young people in discussions and discourse. High level education materials are important additionally to high tech and IT based products and services regarding the topic. Also young people need transparent information about products and materials which they do understand. To reach these target group topics such as new textile fibres, wood in cosmetics or bio-based packaging materials, etc. could be tackled. Additionally to young people families and grandparents were identified as important target groups, as they do have great purchasing power.

The Austrian hub identified industry, administration and research representatives as the target group in one workshop. Here they came to the conclusion that it is important to show the diversity of wood, its potentials or which business areas are in place and discuss possible future market developments.

There have also been other target groups identified, such as politicians, the research and education community, women in general, pensioners and farmers. The most important seemed to be young people and their community, as they are seen as “*pioneers of change*” (Austria hub). The hubs discussed possible formats, topics and time schedules important to reach out to these groups which were elements of the co-designed outreach activities .

Outreach ideas

The co-creation teams came up with a variety of ideas for outreach activities or materials. Not all of them were realizable in the BLOOM project but could work as inspiration for other projects. Table 1 shows an overview on all ideas on outreach activities and materials and important aspects to consider:

Table 2: list of outreach activities and materials

Outreach activity format	Outreach materials	Important aspects and goals
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ TV discussions, outreach webinars ▪ hackathons or “climathons” especially for girls ▪ different kinds of campaigns and advertising ▪ games ▪ lecture series at universities and panel discussions for interested citizens ▪ audiovisual polls and workshops where successful stories are discussed ▪ exhibitions ▪ citizen science projects ▪ competitions between municipalities for the “bioeconomy commune of the year” ▪ a “wood streak” where vlogger make youTube videos ▪ international bioeconomy meetings ▪ ambassadors club for active students ▪ flash mob in shops ▪ village party as platform for communication ▪ trash day (people collect trash for a week) ▪ bring it and segregate it with specialist in bioeconomy ▪ study visits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ market games (women and young families can play a game at the food market) ▪ lifestyle blog ▪ sets of home gardening. ▪ create a model farm to be shared in social media ▪ games (escape room) ▪ printed materials for f2f events ▪ videos and podcasts ▪ collection of tangible objects ▪ teaching materials ▪ tangible products from innovation kit ▪ posters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ participate in existing events such as science week ▪ make use of applications and social networks ▪ combine with tangible and audiovisual materials ▪ make exhibitions more attractive with products and science espressos, games such as escape room ▪ tangible objects and examples for the embedding activities in everyday life environments ▪ create role models

The main goal of all co-creation teams was to communicate what bioeconomy is and what its benefits and critical aspects are and to reach a raised awareness of their target groups on bioeconomy potentials.

Depending on the format of the outreach activity the co-creation groups adapted their focus. For discussions, e.g. TV discussions but also panel discussion or lectures, questions to be raised and tackled during the activity play an important role. Additionally to basic information about bioeconomy as such, questions about who benefits from it, what is new about it, why it is so relevant, how it can be included in everyday life, which role play the different regions or countries, which critical aspects are there and what does it need to reach a sustainable bioeconomy were raised in this formats. When it came to concrete topics the outreach activities or materials should contain, clothing and textiles to be interesting products for the bioeconomy were chosen by several co-creation teams. Bioeconomy products used in everyday life were assumed to be very useful in outreach activities for aiming at raising awareness on bioeconomy. Beside textiles further ideas for such topics have been biomass materials which can be used in sports, fashion, food production, or packaging. For a citizen science project, it was suggested to do a comparative composting experiment with different packaging materials, which could even be done in schools. As the linkage to everyday life might also differ from target group to target group it is important that promoted materials/products are designed in consideration of the target groups interests and activities: “For example, in a fair focused on wellbeing, we should come out with our message in the light of natural cosmetics, bio-based packaging etc. In this case, we should communicate to Alina’s (*that is the avatar’s name, created in the workshop. note author*) kind of target group about the materials, eco-friendliness and health aspects - “*good for you and good for the environment*” (Nordic hub).

When using such products to enter the topic of bioeconomy, questions about the environmental impact of new products, the relation from bioeconomic products to conventional products and the effects of production processes were aimed to tackle the co-created outreach activities. To support a critical thinking of the target group of the outreach activity consumption models, climate change and bioeconomy as a sustainable alternative are suggested topics to be taken up .

Besides social questions such as career options within the bioeconomy overarching topics such as circular economy or megatrends for different industries are gathered outreach activity contents.

For communicating all these interesting topics a definition of bioeconomy understandable for specific target groups is needed. Furthermore, authentic stories, expertise and credibility as well as humour and flexibility for unexpected turns in the communication are noted as core for a successful outreach activity.

General reflection

Reflecting the co-creation activities, it can be stated that one of the most challenging points was to agree on a bioeconomy concept among all participants. Also to bring everybody on a basis to start working took a lot of time. However, even though in some cases the hub leaders wished for more innovative ideas for outreach activities, or it needed further workshops

to reach concrete ideas or go further in depth, the co-creation phase was successful. Many ideas for outreach activities could be gathered, some of them elaborated in detail which led to further implementation. Even though many formats could not be implemented, as they were e.g. too budget intensive to realise, still they serve as input for other people and are also stored at the hubs and wait for later implementation. The co-creation workshops worked well to engage all participants and to gain different perspectives which were included in the outreach formats and materials. Additionally, the co-creation workshops gave insights in what is already known about bioeconomy and bio-based materials in the different hub regions, which was reflected in the later outreach processes.

4.2. Outreach Activities

After the co-creation workshops followed the BLOOM outreach activities, where the hub teams aimed at testing and implementing their co-created ideas. During the outreach period (September 2018 - spring 2021) in total **106 outreach activities** have been implemented by the BLOOM hubs, in which a total of **62.740 people have participated**. Some more activities (e.g. in Finland) will be held in December 2020 (the last project month) or even beyond the project duration and can therefore not be included in this report.

4.2.1 Qualitative analysis

As it was the case in the co-creation activities, also for the outreach activities, the hub teams reported on each of their activities by using a common template. Detailed overview can be found in the overview table in D3.5.

Additionally the hubs collected feedback from participants when they were implementing their outreach activities. The quantitative analysis of these surveys is also provided in this section.

As there were many different outreach formats applied (pre-defined in the DoA, but mainly tailored to specific target groups) they have to be clustered in seven main categories. This section below provides a qualitative analysis of all outreach activities according to these defined categories.

- Gallery walk and Public and Open Space Exhibitions
- Science Espressos
- Webinars
- Visits
- Civic Dialogues
- TV Discussion
- Social Media Campaigns

Gallery walk and Public and Open Space Exhibitions

Basic Information

Hubs found many locations to organise gallery walks and public exhibitions in the different regions. The locations were taking place either in public open space or in semi-public spaces, such as libraries, universities, but also coffee bars, and similar, mostly, rather centrally located in the specific city. Mostly, these exhibitions took place in locations with no obligation to sign in.

The locations were either neutral or easy accessible for unspecified bypassers, or they were particularly related to the topic to reach out for a certain audience, such as for instance a gallery walk at the entrance foyer of the Central European Biomass Conference in Graz, or targeting at participants of the Congress about innovation in bioeconomy. Activities also took place at locations where an interested population could be met, for example a local environmental market, researchers' nights, environment day, an event on regional food products, or an organic food and cosmetic market.

Due to the COVID Pandemic, gallery walks also took place online which allowed for a longer period of presence (41 days and more). Otherwise the duration of the events were very different, ranging from just a few hours, or several times a week, several days (e.g. at the bioeconomy week in Sweden), onto ten days in a row (at the Dutch Design week).

Some formats took place unguided, but many were looked after by an exhibition guide or experts of the hub teams. They were either present all the time, or at certain dates only or one could get a guided tour on demand. Naturally, this was of special interest for schools who could visit the exhibition with their classes at a certain date announced in advance. Besides school classes this format was suitable for all target groups, as the reports of the hubs show.

Format

As already stated, gallery walks worked both ways, either without guidance, when visitors could see the exhibition for themselves, or when they were guided. At different stations or booths, a moderator led a group of visitors from station to station, or there was a moderator at each station. For example at a conference program flyers showed the indicated fix timeslots the hub team had set for the gallery walk. The intention was to have a formed group and that the moderator leads them from station to station with inputs from the experts and a following discussion. But it turned out that on the contrary, people came and left and the event became highly fluctuated. In this case, it worked better to wait until a small group of visitors gathered, and then the moderator was leading them to the gallery walk. Where people seemed most interested, they have been introduced to the expert present or just discussed with the moderator in more detail. This was regarded as high-quality and offered close contact with the participants. However, it was very exhausting for the moderators.

At some events, also experts have been invited, like for instance scientists from the most diverse areas of the bio-economy who provided insights into their research.

BLOOM outreach events were also organised with other specific events or projects (such as the creative circular economy project). Also, collaborations with other organisations and

authorities have been established, such as the Federal Ministry for Sustainability and Tourism (Austria).

Mainly, the gallery walks and exhibitions displayed a range of bio-based products, showcases and materials from companies. Some of the products were really tangible, that audiences could touch and feel them, others had to be protected behind glass (especially in cases, when they were just borrowed), or when they might have become subject to violence or stealing. Especially, in an unsupervised space, the objects had to be treated specially. Depending on the location and country, the events were designed differently, and visitors were given possibilities to approach the event according to their preferences, be it for instance actively engaging them or letting them explore the materials by themselves.

Events of course also used BLOOM outreach materials, which became more and more during the course of the project. They included: BLOOM roll-ups, posters, folders, seed cards, the BLOOM suitcase, tablets (showing the BLOOM quiz for example, or BLOOM videos).

The exhibition events also contained interactive parts, in which the audience could actively get engaged, as for example a quest for teams to design a dish based on kitchen waste and present their recipe.

Other forms of gamifications have been applied as well, especially in events design for younger audiences. Games were for instance identifying certain items by smell or sound etc. and receiving stamps on a card for each correct answer, finally being awarded.

Obviously, due to the more and more restrictive situation because of COVID, less face to face could take place and hub partners tried to convert their activities into online events (Polish Hub).

Content

As the hub leaders had learned from the co-creation process that people do need concrete and real examples about bioeconomy and bioeconomy products and that they want to touch and feel them, gallery walks and public exhibitions showed a huge variety of bio based products, often related to the specific regional topics of the respective hubs (e.g. wood focus in the Northern hub). Products ranged from samples, to showcases and information materials on specific products. At the events, hub leaders were showcasing real examples and also cases of what possibilities and potentialities the bioeconomy has. Visitors were especially interested in information on properties of the textiles, where you can buy them and where they can best be applied. Hub leaders were challenged to provide all this information. Hub leaders also found that mostly, the samples and the information they have provided at the event was totally new for their audiences. Hubs also invited representatives of companies who could tell about their products in more detail.

Another challenge for the hub leaders was to put bioeconomy in a broader context, giving more information about sustainability, and linking all the examples together, to “create the big picture” of the topic (Nordic hub), embedding the topic in climate issues (replacement of fossil fuels) etc.

The hubs tried to embed their activities in regional or national strategies or programs and tie certain activities to specific objectives. For instance a public exhibition linking activities of the Austrian Mission Statement on Bioeconomy on different political levels and discussing its implications and opportunities and showcasing some of the products that are already

produced under this concept. This specific event brought international bioeconomy experts and civil society (in the form of CSOs, the BLOOM school, etc.) together to discuss implications and opportunities of bioeconomy strategies on a European and Austrian level.

A main objective of the hub outreach events was to raise awareness on the subject of bioeconomy. Of course, information about the BLOOM project was shared in all the events as well. The galleries and exhibitions wanted to show real and innovative products, show practice examples and make bioeconomy graspable. At the events, visitors were confronted with questions, such as: What is bioeconomy? Why do we need it? But also with questions such as: Why is biodiversity crucial for food production? The activities also wanted to stimulate discussion on the topic. The hub teams not only gave information on products, but also stimulated political and social questions that arise on the way to a bio-based economy to be discussed with their participants at the events. Furthermore, they gave insights into the whole value chains of the products they presented.

Although the outreach events were tailored to specific groups, in general the BLOOM outreach activities aimed at reaching out to people from different backgrounds and age groups. This goal was widely reached, as all different target groups could be reached via the exhibitions and gallery walks, including young and elderly people. In terms of numbers the events differed a lot, as many circumstances influenced the influx of visitors: bad weather hindered people to attend events in open space, the upcoming corona crisis held people back from direct contacts, lack of advertisement, that people simply did not find or know about the event, while others generated enormous outreach, especially those interlinked with partner events. Some places became even too crowded, especially in public space or waiting areas, activities were often disturbed and lively discussions or longer talks could not have been carried out sufficiently. Some locations were limited by lack of space, be it booths standing too close to each other, or exhibition areas which could only host certain amounts of visitors at the same time.

Gallery walks were also used to show whole production mechanisms on specific products, what are their features, which benefits or what possible challenges do they have and to why they are developed, i.e., to what problems are they seeking new solutions to. They also brought conventional products in comparison to bioeconomy products and discussed if there could there be competitive materials to the usual. In that sense, the events tried to contribute to opinion forming and increase transparency of information to the public.

Additionally, these public events were also meant to get people to share their experiences in the various social media channels opened by the BLOOM project and also to interlink them with other outreach activities of the project, such as a picture competition on Instagram by encouraging visitors take pictures of the event and post them on Instagram with the proper hashtags.

In most of the cases the audiences showed very positive reactions and in general have been open and interested to the topic. Asked afterwards, they often declared that they had learnt something new. But of course, there were also sceptical visitors, some remained interested and sceptical, and asked critically for certain details, such as: Is it really all naturally based? Can it really compete with fossil based products? Some reactions were rather amazed but others could not really believe what they were shown. "Another girl did not believe that paper and (some)t-shirts are made out of wood. She said to me: "no, you are a liar!" But after

some very basic explanation, she said to her father: “ok, let’s go, this is too weird” (experience of an Austrian gallery walk). In general, people were appreciating interesting topics and discussions and the wide range of subjects shown at the events. Based on feedback collected at the events, most people did not know about the topic at all before and asked the hub teams to come more often and reach out more, also to daily life locations, such as supermarkets to reach wider audiences. Most of the participants understood BE as great potential, not only as new markets, but also in terms of its ecological impact and potential to address societal challenges of today. However, some of the visitors had the feeling that the event wanted to sell them something and regard bioeconomy as just another thing to make profit.

In conclusion, it can be said that exhibitions are good and resource-efficient ways of reaching out to a large number of people especially when the exhibition can be arranged for a longer period of time. Collaboration with similar projects turned out to be very fruitful and when organizing an exhibition, one could look for other local actors who promote similar topics. Good promotion and advertisement to inform people of upcoming events is crucial, also formats which attract passers are also seen very useful. To help people find the locations, it needs better descriptions and orientation boards. Most importantly, it needs to have more staff in the stand, to be more able to interact with more people, and thus better allow answering all questions.

Science Espressos

Basic information

The location for hosting science espressos varied a lot across and within the hubs. They were held at: festivals sites (e.g. Järvaveckan - a political festival held in the suburbs of Stockholm), public libraries, university cafeterias, science centres, a festival café, a conference centre, in open space, in waiting and entrance areas of related events and many more.

In total, they attracted all different target groups.

The events have been advertised through various channels, via social media (some of them with paid advertisements), the local premises of the location (e.g. the public library), but also the web site of the hub leader and via local event calendars. On site, organisers used A-stands or other information signs to attract interested people.

Most preferred time of the day for the events were evening hours, 5 pm onwards.

Format

A rather typical science espresso was conducted open to the public where people could come to sit in the audience or pass by and listen to the presentation but also join the discussion afterwards. Usually, it was organized face-to-face, i.e. no streaming or using computers. The presentation was held orally and visualisations such as posters and PowerPoint presentations, as well as example products were used. At first usually, the hub representative welcomed the audience and the speaker, explained the concept of the session and told about the BLOOM project. After the intro, the stage was given to the invited speaker(s).

A science espresso usually lasted approximately for one hour, although some of them were lasting longer or some science espressos had the style of a few presentations in a row, comprising different experts, with a presentation and interaction time in between, like for in-

stance: Presentation 20 min, and 10 min Q & A, etc., but mostly it was one hour, with shorter or longer part for inputs, followed by a discussion time, in which the audience had the opportunity to raise questions. Also, the audience had the possibility to come to see and discuss in more detail about the materials and the BLOOM project. Alternatively, the facilitator started interviewing the researcher in order to make the discussion session lighter and more interactive. At the end of the discussion people had the chance to come to touch the product examples and ask questions about them. The materials and examples were present during the whole session so that the performer could refer to them during the presentation and audiences already could have a look at them. The goal was to enable dialogue between the general public and experts on a certain topic to allow them for getting an overview and understanding of the actual research and related products and discussing pros and cons. On the topic of wooden architecture for instance a representative from a wood firm presented the research area, while participants were standing around a wooden wall from Luxhome (example of Austrian hub).

Some hubs duplicated the same formats and repeated them with new visitors at another time or location.

Also, especially, when the science espressos were embedded in larger events, more science espressos in a row were offered, with different experts, who presented topics which were more or less related to each other.

Other combinations and settings were for instance, having experts and representatives from different stakeholders groups (a student, a communicator/activist, a researcher, a research institute/project, a teacher) who could bring in their specific views in the discussion afterwards.

Science espressos have also been combined with other activities or were embedded in wider activities: like for example in a tent and exhibition area, or in the waiting area for an exhibition (such as in front of the MS science, German hub), as part of the Przemiany festival (Warsaw), or as part of a discussion series (such as "Zukunft Bioökonomie?" in cooperation with the University of Düsseldorf – German hub), or in synergy with other exhibitions like "Get inspired from new bio-based and circular materials!" (Nordic hub).

At some occasions also something to eat and drink was offered at the events, which of course, always attracts audiences.

Later (due to COVID Pandemic), science espressos also took place online, in which as much interactivity as possible was intended, and events tried to be lively, so if they were real face to face meetings. Participants were activated with mentimeter polls, quizzes and discussions.

Content

As learned from the co-creation process it was clear that people do need concrete examples about bioeconomy and bioeconomy products. This became a guiding principle in all BLOOM outreach activities and materials, and so in the organisation of science espressos as well. All of the events were equipped with information materials, posters and practical examples, and provided much content besides the discussions with the invited experts.

Main aim of the science espressos was to inform and raise awareness, but also to create curiosity and stimulate questions and discussions on the topic. They wanted to arouse interest

and enhance knowledge on bioeconomy. They also intended to create space for dialogue and exchange of information and knowledge. Another objective was to increase interest for education and jobs within the bioeconomy sector. Within the events they wanted to demonstrate the potential economic, environmental and social impacts of the bio-economy. Within their regions, they also wanted to build and strengthen communities of practice.

Topics presented varied a lot, mainly, they were related to the overall topic of the respective hubs, and thus not covering all the sections of bioeconomy (e.g.: wood – Nordic hub) and involved research topics and experts from the local area to make these works visible. (For a detailed overview of all activities and topics see D3.5). The bioeconomy topics were presented from experts of different kinds, including ethics.

The events also had some catchy names which should provoke discussion, e.g.: “Can wood replace plastics?”. Topics not only informed about current research, but also raised challenges the field of bioeconomy would like to address. (Like “Plastic bottles and fast food boxes - our earth is being littered and important raw materials are becoming scarce! What possibilities do we have for a sustainable development of our planet? What should be changed in the future?” (Nordic hub)

Hub organisers often tried to embed the topics discussed in wider local, regional or national contexts, and provided more information to allow broader discussions. For instance, in a science espresso on wooden products, also the transition of the forest industry towards circularity, the development of public discussion related to forest and how it has changed over the years and future scenarios of forest industry were discussed (Nordic hub).

Hub organisers found that dialogue is the key asset of this format as it turned out that “*people wanted to talk*”. It also came out that people want to have an open debate on pros and cons, for example where it is reasonable to use wood and where not. In this example, people had the chance to discuss with the researcher about the role of the forest industry in promoting sustainable development. People also had the chance to see and feel concrete examples. Sometimes, visitors had already known or heard about some of the materials or products but hadn’t seen them before so this was a good opportunity to concretize them and highlight their potential.

Science espressos offered much space for debate and asking many details related to the topics, which would not be provided otherwise. Often, the pre understanding level of the participants was low and many rather basic questions had to be solved. Questions targeted facts (how much water does it take to produce a shirt from wood), processes (How does it work? Where do the resources come from?), prices and affordability (what are price differences to conventional products? Where can I buy it? Can I build it up by myself? Is there a list of products available?), legal aspects (isn’t it forbidden to use plastic bags already?), or technical details (where does the binding material come from? etc.) from a more mature audience, on to sceptical considerations which needed to be addressed as well (Is this really natural? Does it really work?). Young visitors raised questions like: What opportunities for internships, courses of study or jobs are there for the bio-economy?

If critical voices rose up, they were carefully discussed between the presenter and the audience.

There were also a lot of questions that didn’t quite relate to the original topic but when the audience was interested and the speaker was capable of answering them, they could discuss

on a broader level as well. Bioeconomy and its further potential, also in relation to global issues, sustainability, circular economy, and the climate crisis have been content in the discussions.

Some were also interested, in which way individual activities could affect the improvement of the situation and if individuals could have an impact at all.

Within the discussions, people also expressed their worries, especially in relation to resources used. They raised concerns about the massive use of biomass and over consumption in general.

In terms of knowledge gain, the science espressos could contribute a lot, as they could offer more in depth discussions as well. Hub organisers reported that although sometimes difficult for their audiences, they could take insights home. (*“First: biomass = energy. After the event: biomass = more. What they understood is that you can substitute fossil-based products with natural resources”* – Austrian hub). So, in the given contexts usually the audience understood the topics related to bioeconomy pretty well. Also, people could understand the wider context of BE (*“People got a new way of understanding sustainability. They understood bioeconomy as something that is present in our life”* – Spanish hub).

However, to answer all the questions and topics arisen often there was not enough time as hub organisers reported. Nevertheless people appreciated the intense and qualitative contact that was made possible during the events. Also, the design of the activities was perceived well, the presentation and examples given by the expert mostly were satisfying for the participants as the hub organisers reported. People were very pleased to see concrete material and product examples and that they had the possibility to come and feel them and ask questions about them during and after the Science Espresso.

Unfortunately, not all events could attract a sufficient number of visitors. Even though many were interested about the event (like showed their interest via social media channels), still many actors are competing about people’s free time as there are a lot of events, activities and hobbies people attend, they are expected to be busy and not have time. Also, not all locations were ideally suited, for instance some hidden corners which were too far away from most of the visitors or bypassers that could have stopped by to listen to the discussion. Also, often participants have not been invited in advance, and had to stumble in. But the framework conditions rather asked for active participation and presence throughout the event which made it difficult for bypassers to join. Bigger events with scheduled programs help to guarantee this type of activity more. Also, events located for example near the entrances or along the pathways where lots of people are passing by brings more attention to the activity.

As in other BLOOM outreach formats, also within the format of science espressos in general many positive reactions from the audiences could be gathered. Although participants did not always show interest during the event, within the feedback questionnaires they expressed positive feedback. Hub organisers have reason to hope that the awareness and understanding of sustainability and the potential of bioeconomy have changed among their visitors. Participants claimed that it needs more education on the topic as only few people know about it, especially in countries, where there BE was not already in the public discourse (Polish hub).

To conclude, the science espresso format is a suitable format for a small group of people, of no more than 20 participants, because too large a number of visitors are also a burden to the event. It needs a good facilitation to structure and rule the discussion and to stimulate active involvement of participants. Facilitator and presenter should discuss beforehand the structure of the event and prepare some questions for the participants. Strict time keeping should hinder experts to exceed their scheduled presentation time.

Webinars

Basic information

The webinars were online events which were held via different web meeting spaces, such as Adobe connect, ZOOM meetings, Clickmeeting, or GoToMeeting.

Mostly, they lasted between 1 or 1,5 hours, up to 2,5 hours, in an exceptional case even six hours (which turned out to be too long and was changed for the following events).

The webinars took place at different dates of the day, inclusive evenings.

People had to register for the events. Always many more people have registered than actively took part live in the event. But afterwards recordings were sent to all people who have registered or were broadcasted via other channels (e.g. a local TV station). Also, the presentations were recorded separately and have been made available afterwards on the internet (e.g. at the hub leaders website).

In general, the numbers of participants varied extremely, ranging from just a few participants up to huge numbers of more than 150 registered persons. In cases of a good promotion on social media, e.g. a specially designed Facebook event with paid promotion many more people showed interest: *“775 interested people and 130 claimed to take part in the event”* (Polish hub, webinar on Food waste).

Some of the webinars were organised as joint events with local partners. Additionally hubs organised international webinars as collaborative events across the hubs.

Format

A typical style of a BLOOM webinar started with an initial introduction about the BLOOM project, either live or for example with a presentation of the BLOOM introduction video, followed by the introduction of one or more speakers. One or two hosts or facilitators led through the event. In average 1 to 3 presentations by experts were given and afterwards there was time for questions and answers and discussion.

Presenters used many ways of visualisations, showing pictures, diagrams, infographics and the like to present the topics and recent research and innovation.

During the webinars, also interactive formats were used, such as mentimeter, or other polls (multiple choice as well as open questions) to engage with the participants, get a picture of who is participating, find out about the level of pre knowledge, or fields of interest and also feedback on the event afterwards.

The webinars were streamed online. Thus, people had the chance to participate and present questions for the presenters despite their physical location. So, participants could ask questions in the chat and the moderators and invited experts tried to address all questions.

Questions were also collected and then forwarded to the speakers, who answered them in a written way afterwards. Many questions we raised in the subsequent discussion during the webinar.

This format caused numerous, partly unpredictable technical issues in various ways, including for instance hindering registered participants from participating, (but at least they could receive recordings afterwards). Or at the speakers side, when for example the webcam – although tested beforehand – suddenly did not function any more, or there was no sound possible, or in general a bad sound quality etc. Organising teams of course did rehearsals beforehand, and also prepared some plans B in cases something went wrong, such as an alternative platform which did not require registration (and when the technical problems would be insoluble the team could just send the link to new platform), or also providing additional technical staff during the event who could be only taking care of these problems.

Content

With regards of topics addressed, similar to other BLOOM outreach events, the topics tackled at the events varied a lot, not only covering different fields of bioeconomy, but also different aspects and angles related to the topic, for instance jobs in the bioeconomy, products, research challenges, controversial discourse such as land use and competition for land, and also related and contextual topics, such as sustainability, climate protection, biodiversity, transport systems, technical challenges, energy issues etc.

This seemingly also helped to increase people's understanding about the diversity of the bioeconomy field. In general, the webinars provided a clear view on specific segments of the topic, presented real life examples, and also about regional and the national bioeconomy strategies (as for example also presenters from ministries or regional councils were invited) also giving insights about the work that has been done regionally to promote bioeconomy by showcasing different bioeconomy projects.

The invited researchers offered an overview of their studies and a summary of applications and products in their specific sector.

Webinars for the general public focused more on awareness raising whereas webinar for participants who knew already about bioeconomy were more focused on knowledge transfer. Therefore, for some participants, it was an eye-opener for new topics whereas for other participants it was more important to bring in their own position on the topic and exchange with others. This enriched the discussions, even if the broad view on the topic could not always be maintained. Even controversial discussions on various problems which have been identified during the discussion have been carried out, bringing in lots of considerations on effects of bio economy. Furthermore, definitions of bioeconomy were questioned during these discussions, such as if wind and solar energy also belong to the bio-economy or not. At some points, not all questions could be answered, also due to lack of expertise of the speakers in specific fields.

Webinars were also a good means to clarify specific questions such as the difference between "biodegradable" and "compostable" (Austrian hub).

The webinars were also used for teaching opportunities, when teachers made their students watch the webinar (or parts of it) during a lecture and after each presentation they discussed it within the classroom.

Also, the events addressed specific groups with specific needs. For example, young people who worked on their projects that were to be presented at the Przemiany festival, had the opportunity to consult their projects with an expert and make necessary corrections thanks to the knowledge gained during the webinars (Polish hub).

Topics addressed current issues as well, such as the Corona Pandemic which demands even more plastics in our daily life – gloves, additional plastic bags etc. So the hub team decided to discuss this subject and explained and discussed which solutions or better alternatives for the future bioeconomy could offer. Plenty of examples of bioeconomy products were presented, for example many kinds of insect larvae eating polyethylene or fungi, actinomycetes and bacteria decomposing etc. (Polish hub)

Due to the online format, and the relatively short duration, webinars often offered a rather dense program, which also asked a lot from participants. Often, much discussion, and a wide range of issues have been raised during the discussions, however, also due to the high number of presentations, the time for questions was reduced and discussions sometimes had to be cut.

Nevertheless, mostly, the gathered feedback was very positive, people found the events almost always interesting and relevant, containing useful information, and stated that they have learned a lot.

Feedback results and questions raised by the participants also showed how much they were touched by the subject and how much it affected them personally. And it showed how the topic sparked interest in overarching topics such as climate protection as well. Questions also show the diverse interests and concerns of participants, like for instance this list of questions, all collected at the same outreach event (of the Polish hub):

- Do insects generate micro plastic by eating plastic – if they do not digest it?
- What is the lifetime of a bioplastic if it's used as an implant?
- Are biopolymers safe for human health?
- Can we buy products from PHA in Poland?
- Is it possible to check the amount of plastic consumed if you're drinking from a plastic bottle?
- How can bioplastics be used in construction /architecture?
- Does cutting the bioplastic accelerate its decomposition?
- What is the bioplastic's temperature resistance?
- Is the bioplastic production process environmentally friendly since acetone is used for the production?
- Do plants also contain micro plastics due to being on the lowest level of the trophic pyramid?
- Is bioplastic production expensive? What needs to be done to make this process profitable on an industrial scale?

During the discussions, often the need for increased use of bio-economy was expressed to answer today's challenges, such as climate change. People felt more positive and interested towards bioeconomy and they expressed that they wanted to find out more information regarding the topic.

In general, webinars are a very appropriate means (especially in times of COVID) to bring the topic to people's homes and discuss with them at different knowledge levels. No one needs to go somewhere and it causes no travel costs, which makes the threshold to participation low. Visualisations can be applied easily and also interactive formats for engaging works, including online debates. Also, the recordings can be used further on, also for teaching purposes. However, it is challenging to compete in the online world with virtual events. Collaborations and synergies with bigger events help to get wider audiences. Furthermore, this also increases the impact on the regional networks, as many different stakeholders can be integrated in the activities as well.

However, webinars also raise many technical issues that need to be addressed and that also cause additional resources which need to be considered. This format is very open, allowing for easy access to the event; still it needs to be targeted to certain groups and designed according to their needs.

The tendency to present too much content in a short time needs to be avoided and therefore, content has to be carefully selected. Also, enough time for breaks need to be considered. Speakers have to be briefed, including technical details as well.

Visits - study trip and innovation route

Basic information

During the co-creation workshops the importance of showcase was emphasised. Thus, the basic idea of the visits was to travel with a group to hot spots of bioeconomy and research and get information first hand, thus the requirement for look and feel and the opportunity to ask detailed questions were intended to be addressed by this format. The visits took a few days (including travel) or at one whole day (for a regional visit). Different stops of the visits tried to have a look at the specific topic from different angles, and to get in contact with different actors related to that field.

Format

Within the BLOOM project, 2 study trips have taken place (due to the COVID situation no more face to face visits with travel could have been carried out unfortunately).

One trip was from Austria to Wageningen (NL), with a group of students (Austrian, Dutch hub), one was in Andalusia (Spanish hub) with 36 participants.

The Dutch trip was a mix between lectures, visits, hands on activities, tours and talks. To make them more interactive the discussion was steered with flash cards, where everyone had to write down their thoughts, for instance at the beginning with questions on what they think what bioeconomy is and how they integrate bioeconomy in their life. The tour included a walk through the bio labs, a tour of the world horticulture centre.

It was a mixed method with hands-on experience and tours and presentations and lectures. The visit was hands on including milk tasting.

Content

At the Netherlands trip, after insights into what the university is doing and what they are researching, the first input addressed the topic "what is bioeconomy in general". This was followed by a tour through the Bio labs of the university showing bio based plastics, and

biobased packaging. This tour was followed by critical discussion on the topic "How good is biodegradable plastic". On another day the group got to know innovative techniques for circular economy in the glass houses. This was followed by visiting a glass house where the group was able to see the latest techniques applied there. Another visit was on a floating Farm on the subject of the circular economy in the city. This is a prototype which serves the closer networking through farm living and city living. Also, the trip toured through mushroom cultivation. Then the participants got the chance to build their own mushroom farm. In Spain, the content of the outreach activity was to show to the general public and private sector practice examples regarding bioeconomy. Examples shown were: The revalorization of tomato production by-products (bio refinery), and the revalorization of wine production by-products into cosmetics.

In general, these trips caused interested and excited reactions of the participants and they could grasp many advantages of the concepts, such as positive impact for the environment, however, also disadvantages such land competition came up as well.

In conclusion, the format worked well and could also be applied for other target groups. The learning and insights are manifold and often very practical as well, as for example to see how to build your own mushroom farm.

Civic dialogues (Workshops / Round tables and panel discussions)

Basic information

Civic dialogues addressed the different target groups which were identified in the co-creation process. For targeting young people activities took place in school events or even dedicated lessons. Also university courses were chosen for implementing round tables there. Thus, students of different ages were targeted and engaged. To reach even more people, activities were also linked to bigger events planned by the hubs organisations; e.g. the science and media congress by Copernicus Centre in Poland, which is an annual meeting of about 100 scientists, journalists and activists, who are willing to improve science communication skills and to gain further knowledge. Other hubs decided to implement their activities in well-known buildings and conference rooms. Others decided for public spaces or places with a cosy atmosphere such as art and coffee bars.

The durations of these civic dialogue formats varied. Shorter formats were chosen for activities in schools, online activities, or workshops at events. Longer formats between 4 and 6 hours were chosen for e.g. deliberative workshops.

The main target groups of these kinds of outreach activities were the scientific community including teachers and researchers, students and pupils and the broader public. The panel discussions reached out to a larger group of people but did not engage them at the same level as the deliberative workshops or round tables did.

Format

The civic dialogue format activities aiming at a public conversation on particular topics of societal relevance differed a bit from each other. The hub teams decided to apply classical workshop formats, such as world cafés, market places, round tables, break-out group discussions, brainstorming sessions, speed dating sessions and lectures and video inputs. All hubs emphasized the importance of working with concrete examples in their civic dialogue

activity. These examples were adapted to the target groups and ranged from bio-based beauty masks, to bio-rubber wheels, bio-plastic bags or the highest wooden building. These formats and examples served to raise questions and to foster discussions among.

Workshops took place face 2 face and later, due to the corona pandemic, online. Hubs decided for interactive online formats, allowed for working in smaller groups and discussions in plenary.

Other formats chosen were panel discussions which were implemented online, due to the COVID situation. In one case the BLOOM suitcase³ was used to give examples for bioeconomy products and to further discuss the topic. In another panel discussion the teams worked with questions raised and voted for and continued discussing myths.

Hubs reported about technical issues they faced in their online workshop formats, and once again emphasized to be aware of the role of the moderator in such a format. For young people it proved that unusual examples raised the highest interest of the target group, especially young men. Outreach through workshop formats has the limit of engaging an open number of people. However, it works well to raise questions and foster detailed discussions. It is also a welcomed format for exchange of knowledge and experiences.

Content

The main objectives of these kinds of outreach activities were to raise awareness and improve knowledge about bioeconomy, to reach discussion about benefits and challenges in the field of bioeconomy, to share information about potentials of bioeconomy and to build and strengthen a community practice.

To reach these objectives different topics were raised in the civic dialogue outreach activities. They range from broader topics, such as definitions of bioeconomy and bioproducts, or societal challenges (growing population, economic growth, climate change), to the dichotomy of bio-technological versus ecologic-economical approaches. Different aspects of sustainability were also chosen topics in the activities. Groups tackled topics like wise use of biomass, sustainable lifestyle, biodiversity in farming and sustainability of bioeconomy products in general and ecolabels. Topics regarding bioeconomy materials and products were packaging, textiles, biocomposites, the huge field of food, its modification, waste and biomass in general.

These topics led to deeper discussion, where questions were raised and unclarities came up. Regarding products questions addressed product characteristics such as durability, recycling processes, product design, safety issues, costs or biodegradation. Further discussion tackled the question or raw materials, biodiversity and availability of resources. Other teams discussed roles in the bioeconomy, and its awareness level among consumers and even manufacturers. In summary the discussions raised critical questions and the outreach format enabled critical discussion of bioeconomy. Bioeconomy was not seen as generally sustainable, but many sustainable practices and examples align with it.

³ Short video showing what the BLOOM suitcase looks like and what it contains:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2fOGs3f-PoI&t=10s>

The content of the activities was in general understood well, even though background knowledge about bioeconomy varied a lot among and for some participants the term bioeconomy was not familiar before the event.

The reaction of the participants was mostly open and interested. People are very curious about the topic. Stakeholders participating in the civic dialogue activities were open to learn more and even interested in applying aspects in their sectors.

The hub reports give a list of potentials of bioeconomy, which were gathered in the civic dialogues. Many address the field of sustainability, as people see potential for smaller CO₂ footprints, less waste, a transition to a more sustainable economy, for replacing plastics, local availability of resources, and a transition to a more sustainable way of production. Furthermore, bioeconomy can positively affect rural areas, lead to more jobs there and play an important role for revitalising.

However, there are also reservations and barriers which were identified in the discussions. People are concerned about cascading biomass resources and global consumption. Costs are also a limitation people care about. How much are consumers willing to pay more for bio-based products and are the products credible in the eyes of consumers? Also constant economic growth is seen as a barrier for bioeconomy. On a human level ignorance and lack of trust regarding bioeconomy has to be mentioned here. People participating in the outreach activity did not believe that bioeconomy is necessarily sustainable, but as aforementioned, still saw it's potential.

The processes followed interactive formats, mixed with presentations, video inputs and lectures. Most important were the examples for bioeconomy in the best case tangible ones or well-presented ones. Hubs provided examples for their topics, such as different forms of packaging materials (Sulapac, Paptic, Jospak) or different materials for textiles (Pinatex, Banana textile, Paper leather, Hemp textile, etc).

In summary the formats worked well, as discussions could be raised and people's interest was high. Lessons learnt were to plan sufficient time, to focus with questions as good as possible (better fewer questions, but more focussed), using success stories and bio-based products to help participants to understand the concept of bioeconomy.

TV Discussion

Basic information

The setting for the TV discussion was a webinar. It lasted 60 minutes and reached stakeholders and representatives from the scientific community, business and industry, policy makers, civil society organisations, general public, media, education, pupils and students. A total number of 318 people could be reached and 100 took part actively.

The target group of this activity were young European citizens and the activity put its focus on regions.

Format

The discussion was uploaded on Austrian regional TV platform Dorf-TV. Around 200 people viewed the discussion on the platform. Based on the results of the co-creation workshop this discussion was broadcasted. Due to the corona crisis it was not possible to do the discussion live for at the TV providers site.

A short introduction about the project and then about real life examples was given. The general method was a webinar, but more specifically it was a discussion of experts with subsequent discussion with participants.

Unfortunately the activity had to be adapted to make it Corona-fit. That was the reason that it became a webinar discussion and was uploaded on the platform. However, the format worked to have a discussion, reached many viewers and made it possible to reach out to the local public.

Content

The discussion tackled the topic of regional development and potentials of bioeconomy for rural areas. The main question for this event was “How does the general public benefit from bioeconomy?”

Throughout the discussion questions about bioeconomy’s standing in Austria, importance of bioeconomy in regions, job options in the field of bioeconomy, bioeconomy in schools, and about an economy without oil and without non-renewable raw materials. Participants were further interested in promoting the development of bioeconomy through federalism, or raised critical aspects about converting biogenic resources into energy, which is not necessarily a good alternative. Other important points raised from participants targeted high costs or soil loss.

Seemingly, the target groups were understanding the content. Students raised many questions, pupils stayed listening. The audience had basic-medium knowledge about bioeconomy. They were interested and sceptical. The discussions showed that participants see reservations and barriers in prices, land use and sustainability.

Many people could be reached in this format. However, the team had to tackle technical issues.

The main objective, reaching the public and discussing the benefits of bioeconomy for the general public, could be reached. Also awareness raising was successfully achieved.

Game

Basic information

The Polish hub team implemented a co-created game for families with children. It took place at an organic food and cosmetic market, which is organised every Sunday. The activity was available for 4 hours. Face to face communication was a key-element in this format.

Format

This outreach activity targeted the general public, by-passers, elderly and retired. Around 40 people participated. The game was combined with a gallery walk, where five stands about different bioeconomy topics were presented. There were also tasks for children, like recognising a herb by its smell or a seed locked in a tin by the sound. Kids gained stamps for right answers. The hub team provided roll ups, cards for collecting stamps, black boxes and props for sensoric tests.

Content

The main topic of this activity was food, how much is wasted, and biodiversity in food production. The target group understood the content of the activity. As this game took place in public space and engaged “by-passers”, there was a great diversity in background knowledge about the topic. However, it can be said that the majority did not know the term bioeconomy. Reactions were very positive. The people liked the format and the content.

The team provided a general introduction into bioeconomy where they admitted to food, feed, bioenergy, biofuels, and biomaterials.

In general the interest of the people at the market was not that high. Only very few “bypassers” participated. Foreigners' interest could be raised. Additionally it was a rainy day that was the reason why relatively few children were at the market. Lessons learnt from the activity were to have communication materials in the national language and English, an early promotion of events, and to make sure to have sufficient space for the activity.

Social Media Campaign

Basic info and Format

The social media campaign took place between 20th and 27th of September 2019. It increased the traffic for BLOOM's website by 60%. The engagement was expected to be higher. The campaign ran on Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram and Facebook and reached a total of 41.536 impressions and 1.292 engagements. Unfortunately the campaign could not reach outside BLOOM's bubble.

Content

The campaign targeted 8 different topics starting with climate change and sustainable society, circular bioeconomy, bioeconomy in daily life. A further block was about forest-based bioeconomy and its potential. In that regard the campaign also discussed what renewable means and showed that “all” things made from fossil-based materials can be made from wood. The third topic targeted bio-plastics and biodegradability. The fourth wood-based fashion in daily life, the fifth block addressed the new innovations, research and production taking place within bioeconomy. In the sixth block they asked how bioeconomy leads to sustainable development. The seventh block talks about what can be done to prevent more human impact on the climate and the last block, number 8, raised the issue if people care about climate and if they care about bioeconomy. This approach was rather a one way communication. No discussion happened on the platforms. However, the campaign got many likes and also retweets, which lets assume that people understood the content.

Participant feedback questionnaires

In total 295 feedback questionnaires were filled in. Almost half of them were filled in after events in Austria and about a quarter after events in Finland.

The answers are analysed according to age, change of knowledge, differences between gender and countries, and differences according to type of activity.

Age

Respondents were on average 33 years old, the youngest was 16 and the oldest 72. In figure detailed distribution.

Figure 5: Age of respondents

Change of knowledge – impact of event

In average the knowledge of participants was higher at the end of the events in comparison to the estimated level of knowledge before the events by 1.7 points. This is a significant gain in knowledge as the paired sample t-test shows ($T=-17.947$, $df=290$, $p=0.000$).

The following figure shows the overall distribution of change in knowledge. One person indicated to have less knowledge after the event by 4 points. Two people seemed to know slightly less with 1 point less after the event. For 58 people or about 20% the level of knowledge remained the same. However, for the majority, i.e. 79%, the level of perceived knowledge increased between 1 and 8 points on the Likert scale of the questionnaire.

Figure 6: Change of knowledge

Attitude

While the level of knowledge seemed to change with the participation in the event for most participants, the attitude towards bioeconomy changed only for about half of the participants. For 51.5% the attitude did not change, while for 47.1% it did change.

For those, who noted a change of their attitude towards bioeconomy, only 1 person indicated that it changed negatively. About 18% felt more informed about bioeconomy, 26% indicated that they had become more curious and 4% that they perceived bioeconomy more critical.

Differences according to demographic data

No gender differences in terms of gained knowledge and change of attitude. Slight correlation between age and knowledge gain: the older the participant, the less perceived knowledge gain ($r=0.313$).

Differences between countries

In all countries the level of knowledge increased significantly (paired sample t-test with $p=0.000$).

A detailed overview shows the following figure.

Figure 7: Change of knowledge according to origin of participants

Differences according type of activity

The knowledge gain seemed to be the highest in the online workshop format. However, the figure above has to be interpreted with caution as in some cases there were only a few respondents.

Figure 8: Change of knowledge according to type of activity

Open question analysis

Asked, what they really liked in the outreach activity, assessing the quality of the invited **experts and given lectures**, participants appreciated, when they could meet “exciting” or “prestigious guests”, when the experts were “well prepared”, “technically sound”, and “competent” and had “much knowledge”. They liked when experts were “offering interesting insights and perspectives”, but also when they were “raising unpopular opinions”, “having their own point of view” and brought in other perspectives, also representing “different branches” and bringing insights from other countries. What concerns the way of the presentation, participants valued “vivid and tangible lectures” with engaged and “natural” inputs, and a “comprehensive and clear structure”. They liked when experts had the “ability to communicate” and “the language was “not too scientific” and “easy to follow”. On the contrary, participants disliked when it was “hard to follow”, when lectures were “too abstract”, or only “university language” or English was spoken, or the speech was simply “too fast”.

Concerning **topics** outreach participants appreciated the “innovative, relevant and interesting subject”. They stated that they had “learned a lot” and “new things” and could broaden their “world view”. They also appreciated when a “wide spectrum” with “a variety” of topics was presented, when topics were “relatable” or “practical” and when “facts could be used later on”. “Clear messages” were welcomed, “and no sensational doom scenarios” and when also solutions were presented. On the contrary, participants criticised when “critical aspects were not raised”, or possible “negative effects were not shown”. Some also required “more theoretical input”. Putting the bio economy topic in context and underlining sustainability as the core principle was also mentioned by some visitors.

In terms of **format and organisation**, obviously, participants appreciated when events were “very well organised” and there was a “proper time management”, but they also liked when there was a “nice atmosphere”, a good or “agile”, or “youthful” moderation. In general, participants liked interactive formats, any possibility to raise questions, also in online formats, for instance, via chat and polls, “something to keep the audience awake”, like questions of estimation, mentimeter and the like. Participants appreciated when experts or panels were “reactive” by for example taking questions from the audience or allowed for “open discussions” which also enabled a “fruitful exchange of opinions”, and “respectfully dealing with different topics and opinions”. For better understanding participants highlighted any “visualisations”, figures, or illustrations, also showing product examples and materials, as well as best practice examples and showcases. Also “providing many tips and links for further reading”, and stimulations for (self)reflection were mentioned. Exchange with other visitors or group or team works (especially in school activities) were seen positively as well. What participants criticised was when they have been “left incomplete”, when simply, time was not enough, too much was offered in short time, events have been too “busy” with too much information provided, and finally when time was not enough, to raise specific questions.

4.2.1 Outreach activities in times of COVID 19

How to deal with outreach and public engagement activities in times of COVID when face to face encounters are not or only partly possible and pre-prepared methods and concepts are no longer applicable? This important question affects all the projects which are addressing a quadruple approach in the field of bioeconomy, and naturally, the BLOOM project as well. Therefore we discussed with the hub partners how to make ourselves heard and how virtual alternatives can serve the required needs. We identified main obstacles as envisaged during the outreach and how the project partners tried to overcome them as it has been experienced and collected by hub partners.

In BLOOM the co-created developed activities were planned to be held in a non-virtual environment. Therefore, being no longer able to stick to initial concepts, the hubs had to be flexible and creative to change the formats of the activities. Additionally, they had needed more time for the preparation of the (revised) events, some of the events had to be cancelled or postponed, the outreach teams had to struggle with missing technical skills, both of the audience but also of staff, and constantly, they had to face an increasing number of online events from many project which meant a competition on time and attention. Furthermore, less personal interaction with the targeted groups was complemented by online “multitasking”, meaning the poor presence and focus of participants to just a single activity in front of the computer.

How to catch this attention and how to engage participants and create lively and interesting events was discussed with the hub participants and also in exchange with other ongoing projects, such as Biovoices, Biobridges or BioEast (during a webinar organised by the EuBioNet).

In BLOOM, but not only in our project, partners revised the structure of their events, shortened them, put fewer programs in it and tried to make them more interactive, like using MIRO boards or SLIDO. They used various formats and introduced bio-based products vir-

tually, as they would have done in face-to-face events. Quizzes or informative cards, videos and produced educational materials found their application here as well.

Further experiences which could be recommended for future activities were: provide good instructions how to (technically) join an event, have a clear agenda, make sure you have good speakers with lively and interesting presentations, and offer interaction with the audience through all available social media channels. Somehow unexpected, the Corona influenced switch to online formats not only caused difficulties, but also offered new opportunities. Saving time and money for travel was one of these advantages, also being able to reach out for remote areas, interlink different countries or enable participation in events which would have been less accessible otherwise. Also, events could be recorded and as such be accessible to a wider audience after the event as well. In general, all partners learned new skills and created flexible ideas

5. Website statistics

This section provides an overview on the statistics of BLOOM's website.

The following aspects have been considered:

- 1- Social Network Engagement
- 2- Main pages
- 3- Audience overview: Users, origin, device point.
- 4- Future: SEO – Search Console (key words to enhance users search on bioeconomy projects and general information)

Data Report

Audience overview data allows tracking users interests on bioeconomy per countries. Besides, depending on the specific pages/sections visited by different users, it gives insight if users updated about news, if they download files or if they further visit BLOOM's social networks.

Regarding the web traffic origin, the analysis informs about how users found the BLOOM website and where they come from. Additionally the statistics provide data about which devices website visitors used (phones, laptops, tablets). Contents were adapted accordingly). Ceia3 team continuously controlled BLOOM website's position on google search engine, Bing, explorer, Safari... to improve its visibility and further foster awareness about bioeconomy.

A key part of the analysis is user behaviour. It gives information about which parts of the website are of high interest and which are not. The so-called Bounce Rate provides information about how long users stay on the page. Based on this analysis ceia3 team adapted the website to keep users interested.

An intermediate report was done in 2018. Here the final statistics and this former report are compared.

5.1 Data Summary for the complete period of BLOOM website working

Audience Overview (web traffic): Page sessions since November 23th, 2017 to November 29th, 2020 come up to 814 (an average rate of 271 users per year). A percentage of 85,1% were new visitors and the 14,9% left were returning visitors.

■ New Visitor ■ Returning Visitor

Figure 9: Rate of new and returning visitors

Most of the users came from Canada (14,41%), Spain (9,20%), United States (8,60%), Poland (7,63%), Belgium (6,05%), Greece (5,57%), Germany (5,45%), Finland (4,84%), Austria (4,48%) and Netherlands (4,12%).

Figure 10: Visits per country

The analytics on the web traffic show that 4.278 users visited the website and stayed in average for 01:35 minutes. The “Home” section was the most visited one (44,15%). The visitors to other sections were distributed as follows: “Hubs” 8,37%, “Repository” 8,06%, “Partners” 5,84%, “News” 5,54%, “Objectives and Approach” 5,07%, “School Network” 3,88%, “Login” 2,43%, “Work packages” 2,29% and “Search” 2,15%. Regarding the user’s behaviour, we can point out that, most of the visitors start from “Home” and further moved to “Hubs”.

Título de la página	Número de visitas a páginas	% Número de visitas a páginas
1. BLOOM Project - Home	1.528	35,72 %
2. BLOOM Project - Hubs	358	8,37 %
3. BLOOM Project - Repository	345	8,06 %
4. BLOOM Project - Partners	250	5,84 %
5. BLOOM Project - News	237	5,54 %
6. BLOOM Project - Objectives and Approach	217	5,07 %
7. BLOOM Project - School Network	166	3,88 %
8. BLOOM Project - Login	104	2,43 %
9. BLOOM Project - Workpackages	98	2,29 %
10. BLOOM Project - Search	92	2,15 %

Figure 11: Analyse of visits of each BLOOM website page

Users got to know the website by social media networks with a rate of 57,8% through Facebook, 40,8% through Twitter and 1,60% through LinkedIn. People visited the BLOOM website on their desktop computers (77,76%), mobile (20,88%) and tablets (1.35%).

5.2 Comparison between all the period results to the intermediate report (2018)

In this section the interim report of 2018 and the results at the end of the project are compared. Most obvious was the increase of users throughout the years. In 2018, 119 users were countered and in 2020 there were 814. Moreover, users continuously stayed longer on the website. An increase of 2:51 minutes could be identified. That implies an important change in the behaviour of users of the BLOOM website, progressing from a quick view of the website in the beginning (2018) with less of a minute of presence, to a handy use of it and higher interaction with content provided.

Comparing origins of users between 2018 and 2020, an increase has been detected in the same countries but visitors from new countries were detected as well, such as Argentina, Chile, Brazil, Russia, South Africa, China, Japan, India, Republic of Indonesia or Korea, between others.

Figure 12: geographical spread of visitors

In conclusion, all these results allow to affirm that BLOOM website has performed an important role as BLOOM project window to the world, showing the main updates, news and material produced by the BLOOM hubs, the school network and the media team.

6 Summary

The evaluation activities as described in this deliverable were meant to analyse the BLOOM activities according to the project objectives as described in detail in D5.1. Different evaluation instruments were used to gather data about the activities. Data was centrally collected by the ZSI team and qualitatively and quantitatively analysed. Preliminary results were fed back to the project participants in order to steer and improve the processes during the project duration. Final results are described in detail in this report. This summary shows how the main objectives as formulated in the evaluation strategy at the beginning of the project could be reached, shows shortcomings and also where expectations could be exceeded. The following section is structured according to the list of objectives along its main categories:

- Internal process
- External outreach and impact
- Benefit/outcome

6.1 Internal process

6.1.1 Enabling a smooth internal BLOOM work process

The evaluation instruments as described in section 2 showed how internal processes were scrutinized and internal feedback was gathered. The feedback questionnaires which were used at each of the internal consortium meetings, and which were adapted slightly from meeting to meeting to address the objectives of the respective meetings gave insight in how the team members could comprehend the presented and discussed topics, how they understood their tasks, how they could undertake the next steps etc, and made clear open questions and where more support was needed. It showed that mostly, partners could understand the content provided, and could gain confidence for carrying out their tasks. Open questions could be solved or could be addressed in subsequent meetings. Also, the work package leader surveys gave insight into the needs and requirements of the different work packages and tasks which could not have been anticipated before the activities in the work packages had started. Also, a better internal communication could be organised based on gained insights. Internal communication processes (bilateral meetings, hub alignment calls, or regular hub meetings) were established based on formulated needs.

6.1.2 Learning evaluation: BLOOM consortium as community of practice

The WP 5 team activities as shown in the report at hand aimed at supporting the BLOOM project as a learning organisation. The team established different feedback loops (such as oral feedback at consortium meetings, feedback on outreach reports) continuously supported learning among the team members and helped that experiences could be shared across hubs. Insights have been used to find what needed to be discussed and what needed to be

developed further on. So did for instance, help the two cross fertilisation meetings to reflect on work being carried out and to better design further develop activities and join forces. Evaluation activities which monitored the building up of new networks, i.e. the teachers' networks and regional hub networks showed that school partners and hub leaders could establish or connect to communities of practice. In some hubs however only to a certain extent, especially in regions or countries where there is no public discourse on bioeconomy yet.

6.2 External Outreach and impact

6.2.1 Make bioeconomy knowledge and research available for education

Evaluation results as described in section 3 show how successfully the secondary and tertiary education sector was reached with the project activities. Many of the described co-creation and outreach activities in the hubs were tailored especially for young people and were often visited and used by school classes. Schools could also make use of the various materials developed by the project, such as the BLOOM school box, videos or quiz, which were commended within the feedback questionnaires as well. Outreach formats such as science espressos, gallery walks and webinars (and their recordings) were used for teaching purposes as well. University students furthermore could benefit from special formats such as study visits and workshops in which their projects have been discussed. In general, the school network activities, mainly carried out by partner EUN were assessed very positively and could convince in numbers as well.

6.2.2 Create a virtual bioeconomy platform and repository

The BLOOM website was set up in due time and thus could be communicated throughout all project activities and draw interested people in to look for further information. All BLOOM materials have been made available on the website which functions as a repository as well, other relevant materials can also be found there. Web statistics show that the BLOOM website has performed an important role as BLOOM project window to the world. It caused much traffic and was visited a lot in the project's time. All project hubs are named and described at the platform to allow visitors to find out more about activities and actors in the field of bioeconomy in their region. However, two-way communication at the website did not function as requested, as not many people used the platform for dialogue and exchange. For this purpose, social media were better accepted as the numbers show. Finally, the BLOOM website will be maintained for 5 more years in order to allow the materials still available.

6.2.3 Develop innovative co-creation workshops to involve all perspectives

As described in detail in section 4.1. the hub teams have put a lot of effort to co-create their outreach activities in their specific regions. All co-creation activities (including the virtual ones) were documented within reporting templates which allowed hub teams to reflect on

their activities, exchange with others and receive feedback. Based on that the outreach activities have been developed (as stated in the outreach activity reports). Special emphasis was set to reach out for different stakeholder groups. Reports show that all five stakeholder groups could have been included in the co-creation processes and many innovative ideas could have been developed. However, not all of these ideas could be really implemented in the outreach phase afterwards.

6.2.4 Stimulate activities via regional hubs

The results showed that much local and regional cooperation could have been established by the BLOOM hubs. Many activities were carried out in combination with regional events as the outreach activity reports have described. Hub activities have been scrutinized by regional actors and hub leaders also stated that they could have established good contacts for future activities. Activities took place in different contexts and locations and thus contributed to an extension of the usual offers of local institutions such as libraries for instance. Additionally, many new formats were implemented at sometimes creative locations (which have not been connected with bioeconomy so far) and stimulated discussion there. Activities also sought to bring different stakeholders from the regions (and also internationally) together, which created inter- and transregional collaborations.

6.2.5 Implement innovative outreach activities

As the numbers tell and reports on activities have shown a sufficient number of outreach activities have taken place throughout the project (and more to come even after the project ends), even in times of COVID 19 when outreach and especially face to face formats became very challenging. The outreach activities engaged all kinds of target groups, also such ones, not yet specifically addressed (such as female farmers to discuss bioeconomy and food production). Within the gathered feedback from participants, they tell about their knowledge gained after the activities, how their interest was stimulated and that they would personally pursue the topic further. The activities show how to engage and actively involve the public in a bioeconomy dialogue. The experiences on what works and what doesn't work as reported by the hub teams help to collect lessons learnt for similar activities in the future (as results also fed into the BLOOM policy brief D5.4).

6.3 Benefit /Outcome

6.3.1 Build up and strengthen a bioeconomy community

As previously said, the BLOOM activities involve a range of different stakeholders and target groups and made the topic of bioeconomy visible in the regions of the hubs. Especially in regions and countries in which bioeconomy is already part of policy strategies, the BLOOM activities and partners were well perceived and also integrated in existing communities. Furthermore, many sister projects exchanged with the BLOOM project and also conducted joint activities, such as mutual learning seminars and conferences which helped to

strengthen further collaboration. Besides their outreach participants, also the partners have declared (during the final dissemination event) that they have learned a lot, not only in terms of co-creation and outreach methodology, but also in the field of bioeconomy. Many of the consortium partners had been confronted with the topic for the very first time. As for now, some of them are already involved in follow up projects on bioeconomy, and others will continue their long-lasting work on bioeconomy in their regions.

7 Resources

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Marschalek, I.; Handler, K. Holoher Ertly, T.; Smoliner, S. 2011. Evaluation Strategy Plan. NanOpinion. FP7 Grant Agreement No. 290575.

Links:

http://evaluationtoolbox.net.au/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=24&Itemid=125

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Smallman, M.; Handler, K.; Schrammel, M.; Hofer, M.; Miller, S.; Voigt, C. 2015. D5.2 Methodologies and tools for Internal Formative Evaluation. Set of turn key evaluation designs including questionnaires and templates to perform formative evaluation processes throughout the project. RRI-tools. FP7 Grant Agreement No. 612393.

Schrammel, M.; Feichtinger, J. 2019. D5.2 Monitoring Instruments. BLOOM. H2020 Grant Agreement No. 773983

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